

The Role of Group Chairman and Extension in Bogor District in Improving the Performance of Fisheries Group in the Pandemic Time of Covid-19

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Abstract:- Research on group performance was carried out on fishery groups in Bogor Regency for 2 months from April to May 2021, 40 fishery groups were taken randomly. Descriptive, qualitative data analysis, cross tabulation and Spearman rank correlation test with the aim of obtaining a relationship between group performance during the COVID-19 pandemic with various factors that influence it. Research results as of October 2020 there is 260 fishery groups, as many as 82% over the age of 7 years have been established for more than nine years, meaning that the growth of these groups is on average in 2013, until the research has only reached the middle class. In the age range of the group, the low performers were 16.3% and the high performers were 3%. A total of 10.5% of the beginner group were low performers and 1.8% were high performers. A total of 32.5% of the low-performing middle group and 8% of the high-performing group. The role of group administrators is 13% low, and 18.5% is high. The role of fishery instructor was high in 33.7% of the group, and low in 9.6% of the group. Group internal factors were significantly negative (-0.303) - (-0.528) with group performance. The role of group administrators, the role of extension workers has a weak correlation with group performance. The role of administrators has a weak relationship with group performance and the role of fishery instructors does not have a significant relationship in improving group performance.

Keywords:- External Factors, Role, Group Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Group performance assessment is an important factor for the success of group performance management, so it has a direct picture of the group's strategic plan. Performance appraisal is often an activity that is disliked and negative and is considered to require no expertise, even though it is especially important during the Covid 19 pandemic. The

influence of the Covid 19 pandemic is known to have significantly reduced the performance of various businesses and activities. Likewise, the fisheries group in Bogor Regency, which previously performed well, since the Covid-19 pandemic, many have become powerless and many have even fallen into suspended animation. However, there are still a number of fishery groups that are able to maintain good business conditions for their members. Group factors with high and low performance need to be identified as a reference in coaching. In Bogor Regency until 2021 there are 260 fishery groups. Based on this data, we want to know which groups are still working high, how many are stagnant, and how many are decreasing. The performance of the fisheries group is related to the age of the group, class of the group, the role of the group leader and the role of extension workers and related agencies. Group performance is work performance or actual achievement achieved by the group which is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by the group in carrying out its functions in accordance with the responsibilities given. Performance or group performance itself according to Nurlaila (2010) is the result or output of a process. Meanwhile, from the aspect of the behavioral approach in management, group performance is the quantity or quality produced or the services provided by the group performing its function (Luthans, 2005). The condition of the existence of low-performing, medium-performing and high-performing groups during the Covid-19 pandemic has not yet obtained much data on related factors. In this regard, research needs to be conducted to determine the factors related to the performance of fishing groups during the Covid 19 pandemic.

The framework of this research is to see the close relationship between independent variables (X) including group internal factors (X1), the role of group administrators (X2) and the role of Fisheries Extension (X3) on the dependent variable, namely group performance (Y) as shown in Figure 1.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research done in Bogor Regency. The research was conducted for 2 months from April to May 2021. Respondents 40 fishery groups in Bogor Regency were taken randomly 2 groups per district. The data collected consists of primary data and secondary data. Data analysis was carried out descriptively, qualitative analysis was carried out for all research purposes, quantitative analysis was carried out to test the proposed hypothesis. Internal characteristics and external characteristics were measured by cross tabulation analysis and by using frequency distributions and mean values. To measure the closeness of the relationship between variables, Spearman's rank correlation test is used, with the formula:

$$R = \frac{N(\sum XY) - (\sum X \sum Y)}{\sqrt{[(N \sum X^2) - (\sum X^2)][(N \sum Y^2) - (\sum Y^2)]}}$$

Information: r = correlation coefficient, N = number of cases, X = first measurement result, Y = second measurement result.

To interpret the correlation results, the Guilford rule (Rakhmat, 2001) is used as follows: < 0.25 : very weak closeness, 0.26 – 0.50 Correlation is sufficient, 0.51 – 0.75 strong correlation, 0.76-0.99 very strong correlation .

III. RESULTS

The types of fishery groups in Bogor Regency are 91.5% Fishery Groups (Pokdakan), 8.35 Pongolah and Marketers Groups (Poklahsar), and 0.2% Community Supervisory Groups (Pokmaswas). Group ages and group classes until 2021 are as follows.

Fig 1. Group age

Fig 2. Group class

The performance of the fisheries group during the Covid 19 pandemic is based on the 5 (five) indicators as follows .

Fig 3. Four Group Performances During the Covid 19 Pandemic

The results of cross-tabulation between group internal factors (age) and group performance indicators based on the percentage of the number of groups are as follows.

Table 1. % Cross tabulation between age groups and group performance

GROUP AGE	% GROUP NUMBER	GROUP PERFORMANCE INDICATORS											
		PRODUCTION PLANNING			PRODUCTION INPUTS			PRODUCTION PROCESS			PRODUCTION RESULT		
		R	S	Q	R	S	Q	R	S	Q	R	S	Q
1 - 3 years	8	0	8	0	0	7	1	0	7	1	0	7	1
4 – 6 years	10	0	8	2	1	9	0	0	10	0	1	8	1
7 – 9 years	33	5	17	1	4	18	1	8	15	0	6	15	2
Over 9 years	49	11	27	1	10	37	2	10	38	1	11	33	5
AMOUNT	100	16	80	4	15	81	4	18	80	2	18	73	9

Note: R=Low, S=Medium, T=High.

Table 2 . % Cross tabulation between group classes and Group Performance

GROUP AGE	% NUMBER OF GROUPS	Group performance indicators											
		Planning			Input			Process			Product		
		R	S	Q	R	S	Q	R	S	Q	R	S	Q
Beginner	23	11	10	2	10	11	2	8	13	2	13	9	1
middle	77	45	15	7	30	40	7	27	41	9	40	28	9
Main	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Note: R=Low, S=Medium, T=High.

Correlation test results between group internal factors (age, class) with 4 (four group performance indicators as follows;

Table 3. Correlation Test Results Between Group Internal Factors and Group Performance

Group Internal Factors	Group Performance Indicators			
	Planning	Preparation of Saprokkan	Production process	Production result
Group Age	-0.266*	-0.303*	-0.217	-0.230
Group Class	-0.518**	-0.348*	-0.528**	-0.429**

*significant at the 0.05 level of confidence

** significant at the 0.01 kepercayaan confidence level

The role of group administrators during the covid 19 pandemic, based on 5 (five) roles that must be carried out by group administrators and the results of the correlation test on group performance are as follows.

Fig 4. Group Percentage and Role of Group Manager

The results of the test of the closeness of the relationship between the 5 (five) roles of group administrators during the covid 19 pandemic with 4 group performance indicators are as follows.

Table 5. Correlation Test Results of the Role of Group Leaders with Group Performance Indicators

Role of Group Leader	Group Performance Indicators			
	Planning	Provision of Production Input	Production process	Production result
Achievement of Group Goals	0.039	0.161	0.043	0.029
Running Group Values	0.054	0.112	-0.139	-0.190
Meeting the needs of members	-0.099	0.041	-0.130	-0.013
Executing Klp Structure Functions	0.103	0.101	0.036	0.064
Motivate Members	-0.231	-0.223	-0.186	0.115

*significant at the 0.05 confidence level; ** significant at the 0.01 kepercayaan confidence level

The role of fishery instructors as facilitators, motivators, and mediators during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the results of the relationship closeness test are as follows.

Fig 5. Three Roles of Counselors During the Covid 19 Pandemic

Table 6. Correlation Test Results of the Role of Extension Officers with Group Performance Indicators

Extension Role	Group Performance Indicators			
	Planning	Preparation of Saprokan	Production process	Production result
Facilitator	0.066	0.086	0.183	0.130
Motivator	-0.008	0.048	0.042	0.026
mediator	0.023	0.150	0.024	-0.013

*significant at the 0.05 level of confidence

** significant at the 0.01 confidence level

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Group Internal Characteristics

The types of fishery groups in Bogor Regency are based on the Regulation of the Minister of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Number 14 of 2012 concerning Growth and Institutional Development of Main Fisheries Actors, as many as 91.5% of Fisheries Groups (Pokdakan), as many as 8.4 Processor and Marketers Groups (Poklahsar), and 0.2% Community Monitoring Group (Pokmaswas). Based on the results of research from Of the 260 fishery groups, 49% have been established for more than nine years, meaning that the growth of these groups is on average in 2013. However, based on data, there are no groups that have entered the main class, as many as 77% are in the middle class, and 23% are the beginner class. This is as stated by Herlina (fishery instructor) during the pandemic in her working area, many main groups decreased elements and sub-elements of group activities so that during reassessment their scores dropped to the lower classes. In addition, the applicable rules (Regulation of the minister of maritime affairs and fisheries No. 14 year 2012) regarding the Growth and Development of Fisheries Main Actors only regulate 3 classes, namely Beginner, Intermediate and Main, so that the range of grades to move up to the main class is quite high (651-1000), while in agricultural groups are organized into 4 classes (Beginner, Advanced, Intermediate, Main).

B. Group Performance

The results of the study showed that 43.25% of the groups had low performance. 42.25% had sufficient performance and 14.5% had high performance. Preliminary research on the performance of the Pottanae Farmers Group Association as mentioned by Eymal et al (2018) shows that the performance of the Gabpoktan is low or ineffective, only carrying out the role of provider of infrastructure or production inputs, while the four roles (planning, production process, productivity) are still very limited. low. Referring to the opinion of Mardikanto (2015), the performance of a fishing group is a description of the role of people in the group carrying out their main tasks so that they can provide the results set by the group or the description of the role of a group that has carried out all the main activities so as to achieve group goals. The same thing is based on Slamaet Ristanto's research (2021) regarding the influence of the Covid-19 pandemic on bank organizations, that the negative impact only occurs in large bank groups that are more able to survive than small bank groups. The longer the age of the group (more than 7 years) the more the number of groups (82%), but the performance is much lower. In this age range, the group with low performance is 16% in the business planning group, 14% in the production input group, 18% in the production process group, and 17% in the production output group. Meanwhile, those with high performance in this age range were only 2% in the business planning group, 3% in the production input group, and 7% in the production output group. The results of the cross-tabulation showed that the beginner group had an average of 10.5% for the low performing group and 1.8% for the high performing group.

Whereas in the Middle class there were 32.5% of the group with low performance and only about 8% of the group with high performance. The link between age and performance as researched by Karim K (2018) the age variable has a significant positive effect on an employee's work performance. The results of the correlation test between group internal factors and group performance obtained a significant negative value (-0.266) to (-0.528), which means that during a pandemic covid 19, the higher the group age, the lower the performance in aspects of planning and supplying production inputs, as well as the higher the group class, the lower in all group performance indicators.

C. Group Manager Role

Group administrators are chosen so that they gain authority, namely the nature of a communication or order within a group owned by members to carry out a work activity in accordance with their contribution (Prawirosentono, 1999:27). As for the role of group administrators during the covid 19 pandemic, an average of 13% of the group's management role was low, and as much as 18.5% of the group's management role was stated to be high. Thus the role of the dominant board stagnant (68.5%). This was reinforced by the results of the closeness test which showed that the role of group administrators during the Covid 19 pandemic did not have a close relationship to group performance, both with a unidirectional (positive) and inverse (negative) relationship.

D. The Role of Fisheries Extension

The role of fisheries extension officers both in conveying innovation (facilitator), motivating the group to continue to grow and develop (motivator) as well as helping to access information and technology and the needs of members (mediator) is considered to play a high role in as many as 33.7% of the group, and in 9.6% the role group is in the low category. However, this relatively high role does not correlate with increasing group performance. Previous research conducted by Khaeron (2009) found that there is a close relationship between motivation and employee job satisfaction. Although the role of extension workers in motivating group performance is high, it is recognized by as many as 53% of the group. As is the case with the role of group administrators, the results of testing the closeness of the relationship between the role of extension workers and group performance during the Covid 19 pandemic did not have a close relationship to group performance, either a unidirectional (positive) or inverse (negative) relationship.

E. Group Performance Improvement Strategy

Based on the results of the research above, as much as 43.3% of the performance of the fisheries group in low conditions and only 14.5% of the group in high conditions, the strategy to improve group performance is to improve the performance of group administrators and the role of fisheries extension officers, with an orientation towards all group performance indicators such as following picture.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research on the performance of fishery groups during the covid 19 pandemic (1) as many as 43.3% of the group's performance decreased, (2) the higher the age of the group and the group class actually decreased the group's performance (negative close relationship), (3) the role of group administrators was not has a close positive or negative relationship to group performance, (4) the role of fishery instructor, although quantitatively considered high, the results of the close relationship test do not show a positive or negative close relationship to group performance.

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